

Table 1. Multiseason correlated-replicate model selection results for probability of detection for eastern wild turkeys at stations along gobbling call-count survey routes in northern Wisconsin, USA, 2014–2017. Models were ranked by the difference (ΔAIC_c) between the model with the lowest Akaike’s Information Criterion for small samples (AIC_c) and AIC_c for the current model, K is the number of model parameters, w_i is model weight, and $-2\log(L)$ is the maximized -2 log-likelihood function. Model fit was assessed in Program PRESENCE v12.23 (Hines 2006).

Probability of detection model ^a	K	AIC_c	ΔAIC_c	w_i	$-2\log(L)$
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time}^2 + \text{Wind} + (\text{Time} \times \text{Wind})\}, \pi\}^b$	20	3,188.23	0.00	0.979	3,142.06
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time}^2 + \text{Wind}\}, \pi\}$	17	3,195.89	7.66	0.021	3,157.49
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time}^2\}, \pi\}$	14	3,226.15	37.92	0.000	3,195.19
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time} + \text{Wind} + (\text{Time} \times \text{Wind})\}, \pi\}$	17	3,230.49	42.26	0.000	3,192.09
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2 + \text{Time}^2\}, \pi\}$	20	3,231.81	43.58	0.000	3,185.64
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date} + \text{Time} + \text{Wind}\}, \pi\}$	17	3,235.11	46.88	0.000	3,196.70
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time} + \text{Wind}\}, \pi\}$	14	3,235.49	47.26	0.000	3,204.53
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2 + \text{Time} + \text{Wind}\}, \pi\}$	20	3,239.29	51.06	0.000	3,193.12
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time} + \text{Wind} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\}$	20	3,239.54	51.31	0.000	3,193.36
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time}\}, \pi\}$	11	3,247.31	59.08	0.000	3,223.49
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Time} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\}$	17	3,247.39	59.16	0.000	3,208.99
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date} + \text{Time} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\}$	20	3,252.06	63.83	0.000	3,205.88
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2 + \text{Time} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\}$	23	3,255.98	67.74	0.000	3,201.67
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Wind}\}, \pi\}$	11	3,260.60	72.37	0.000	3,236.78
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date} + \text{Wind} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\}$	20	3,263.94	75.71	0.000	3,217.76
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Wind} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\}$	17	3,264.05	75.82	0.000	3,225.65
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2 + \text{Wind} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\}$	23	3,267.40	79.17	0.000	3,213.10
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\}$	14	3,291.09	102.85	0.000	3,260.13
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date} + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\}$	17	3,292.44	104.20	0.000	3,254.03
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2 + \text{Sky}\}, \pi\}$	20	3,296.47	108.24	0.000	3,250.30
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Noise}\}, \pi\}$	11	3,297.09	108.86	0.000	3,273.27
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}\}, \pi\}$	11	3,297.49	109.25	0.000	3,273.67
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Precip}\}, \pi\}$	11	3,298.16	109.93	0.000	3,274.34
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Temp}\}, \pi\}$	11	3,298.18	109.95	0.000	3,274.36
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Season}\}, \pi\}$	17	3,298.32	110.09	0.000	3,259.91
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period}\}, \pi\}$	8	3,298.71	110.48	0.000	3,281.74
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Survey Period} + \text{Date}^2\}, \pi\}$	14	3,302.42	114.19	0.000	3,271.46
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Year}\}, \pi\}$	9	3,302.71	114.48	0.000	3,283.49

Table 1: detection model set

$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{.\}, \pi\{.\}$	6	3,302.92	114.69	0.000	3,290.36
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Full}\}, \pi\{.\}$	41	3,335.12	146.89	0.000	3,223.17
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{Observer}\}, \pi\{.\}$	56	3,355.21	166.98	0.000	3,179.37

^a Model parameters include route occupancy (ψ), local availability at a survey station given unavailability at the previous station (θ), local availability at a survey station given availability at the previous station (θ'), establishment (γ), abandonment (ε), detection (p), and availability at the unobserved survey station defined by the Markov equilibrium process via θ and θ' (π). All parameters besides detection probability were held constant (.) to evaluate the potential influence of environmental covariate(s) on gobbling activity and the ability of observers to detect wild turkeys. Continuous detection covariates were standardized and include time of day (Time), time in quadratic form (Time²), Julian date (Date), Julian date in quadratic form (Date²), average wind speed (Wind), and temperature (Temp). Categorical covariates include annual survey period (Survey Period), study season (Season), study year (Year), sky conditions (Sky; cloudy, partly cloudy, or clear), whether precipitation occurred during the survey (Precip), whether there was a noise disturbance during the survey (Noise), surveyor that conducted the survey (Observer), and a full identity model where detection is different on each survey (Full).

^b Top-supported model ($\Delta\text{AIC}_c < 2$) within the northern Wisconsin detection model set which was further used as the base model in the subsequent model set to evaluate local availability of wild turkeys (Table 2).

Table 2. Multiseason correlated-replicate model selection results for probability of local availability for eastern wild turkeys within 1.6-km buffered (813.7 ha) stations along gobbling call-count surveys routes in northern Wisconsin, USA, 2014–2017. Models were ranked by the difference (ΔAIC_c) between the model with the lowest Akaike’s Information Criterion for small samples (AIC_c) and AIC_c for the current model, K is the number of model parameters, w_i is model weight, and $-2\log(L)$ is the maximized -2 log-likelihood function. Model fit was assessed in Program PRESENCE v12.23 (Hines 2006).

Probability of local availability model ^a	K	AIC_c	ΔAIC_c	w_i	$-2\log(L)$
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}^b, \pi\{.\}^c$	28	3,146.62	0.00	0.478	3,077.94
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}^c$	26	3,146.77	0.15	0.443	3,083.97
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	28	3,150.67	4.04	0.063	3,081.98
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,155.65	9.02	0.005	3,092.85
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	28	3,155.85	9.23	0.005	3,087.16
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,157.53	10.90	0.002	3,094.73
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,158.62	12.00	0.001	3,095.82
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,160.04	13.41	0.001	3,097.24
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	24	3,161.12	14.50	0.000	3,104.03
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	28	3,161.26	14.64	0.000	3,092.57
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,161.83	15.20	0.000	3,099.03
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,162.12	15.49	0.000	3,099.32
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	24	3,162.36	15.73	0.000	3,105.27
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,162.41	15.79	0.000	3,099.61
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{IJI}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,164.02	17.39	0.000	3,101.22
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,164.18	17.56	0.000	3,101.38
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{CWED}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,164.19	17.56	0.000	3,101.39
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	28	3,164.28	17.66	0.000	3,095.60
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{IJI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,164.30	17.68	0.000	3,101.50
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{ENN}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,164.62	18.00	0.000	3,101.82
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,164.79	18.16	0.000	3,101.99
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,164.93	18.31	0.000	3,102.13
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{IJI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,165.12	18.49	0.000	3,102.32
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	24	3,165.22	18.60	0.000	3,108.13
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,165.59	18.96	0.000	3,102.79
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,165.87	19.25	0.000	3,103.07
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	26	3,166.45	19.83	0.000	3,103.65

Table 2: local availability model set

$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,166.51	19.89	0.000	3,103.71
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{ENN}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,166.90	20.27	0.000	3,104.10
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,166.95	20.33	0.000	3,109.86
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,166.96	20.34	0.000	3,104.16
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}^2 + \text{CWED}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,167.06	20.44	0.000	3,104.26
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{ENN}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,167.39	20.76	0.000	3,104.59
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,167.72	21.10	0.000	3,110.63
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{ENN}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,167.88	21.25	0.000	3,105.08
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{ENN}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,167.92	21.29	0.000	3,105.12
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,168.50	21.87	0.000	3,099.81
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,168.66	22.03	0.000	3,111.57
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,168.78	22.16	0.000	3,111.69
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,169.79	23.16	0.000	3,112.70
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,169.97	23.34	0.000	3,101.28
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,170.42	23.80	0.000	3,118.87
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,170.55	23.93	0.000	3,113.46
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,171.06	24.44	0.000	3,119.51
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,172.00	25.38	0.000	3,120.45
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,172.60	25.98	0.000	3,121.05
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,173.10	26.47	0.000	3,116.01
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,173.11	26.48	0.000	3,116.01
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,173.56	26.94	0.000	3,122.01
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,174.29	27.66	0.000	3,117.19
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,174.86	28.24	0.000	3,112.06
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,175.92	29.30	0.000	3,118.83
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,176.46	29.83	0.000	3,119.37
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,176.64	30.02	0.000	3,113.84
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,176.93	30.30	0.000	3,119.83
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,177.15	30.53	0.000	3,114.35
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,117.21	30.59	0.000	3,114.41
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,177.28	30.66	0.000	3,120.19
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,178.17	31.55	0.000	3,126.62
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,178.19	31.57	0.000	3,126.64
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{IJ}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,178.59	31.96	0.000	3,127.03

Table 2: local availability model set

$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,178.73	32.10	0.000	3,127.18
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,178.90	32.27	0.000	3,127.34
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,179.78	33.16	0.000	3,128.23
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{ENN}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,180.14	33.51	0.000	3,128.58
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,180.65	34.03	0.000	3,123.56
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,181.43	34.80	0.000	3,118.63
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,182.32	35.70	0.000	3,130.77
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,182.67	36.05	0.000	3,125.58
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,182.71	36.08	0.000	3,131.15
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,183.13	36.51	0.000	3,126.04
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,183.44	36.82	0.000	3,131.89
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{EDGE}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,183.50	36.88	0.000	3,131.95
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,183.70	37.07	0.000	3,126.61
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,184.06	37.44	0.000	3,132.51
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,184.15	37.53	0.000	3,132.60
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{IJ}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,184.66	38.04	0.000	3,133.11
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,185.63	39.01	0.000	3,128.54
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,186.21	39.59	0.000	3,123.41
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{ENN}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,186.37	39.75	0.000	3,134.82
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,186.63	40.01	0.000	3,135.08
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,186.87	40.24	0.000	3,135.31
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,186.97	40.35	0.000	3,135.42
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{IJ}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,187.62	41.00	0.000	3,136.07
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{IJ}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,188.16	41.54	0.000	3,136.61
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{.\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}^d$	20	3,188.23	41.61	0.000	3,142.06
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,188.48	41.86	0.000	3,136.93
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{STRATA}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,188.51	41.89	0.000	3,119.82
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,189.25	42.63	0.000	3,132.16
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{IJ}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,189.26	42.63	0.000	3,137.70
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CONTAG}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,189.60	42.98	0.000	3,183.05
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,190.76	44.13	0.000	3,139.20
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,190.89	44.26	0.000	3,139.33
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,190.91	44.28	0.000	3,139.35
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{IJ}_{\text{hard}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,191.01	44.39	0.000	3,139.46

Table 2: local availability model set

$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,191.22	44.60	0.000	3,139.67
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,191.45	44.82	0.000	3,134.36
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,191.52	44.90	0.000	3,139.97
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,191.60	44.98	0.000	3,140.05
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,191.69	45.07	0.000	3,134.60
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,191.76	45.14	0.000	3,140.21
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,192.04	45.41	0.000	3,140.48
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,192.16	45.54	0.000	3,140.61
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{ENN}_{\text{ag}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,192.25	45.62	0.000	3,140.69
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{ENN}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,192.89	46.27	0.000	3,141.34
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{ENN}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	22	3,193.07	46.45	0.000	3,141.52
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,193.30	46.68	0.000	3,136.21
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,193.53	46.91	0.000	3,136.44
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	24	3,193.72	47.10	0.000	3,136.63
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	26	3,197.35	50.73	0.000	3,134.55

^a Model parameters include route occupancy (ψ), local availability at a survey station given unavailability at the previous station (θ), local availability at a survey station given availability at the previous station (θ'), establishment (γ), abandonment (ε), detection (p), and availability at the unobserved survey station defined by the Markov equilibrium process via θ and θ' (π). Occupancy, establishment, and abandonment parameters were held constant (.) to evaluate the potential influence of land cover covariate(s) on probability of local availability (θ and θ') of wild turkeys in northern Wisconsin. Covariates include class-level composition and configuration metrics (McGarigal et al. 2012) for agriculture (ag), deciduous forest (dec), forest cover (forest), herbaceous-grassland (grass), upland hardwoods (hard), oak forest (oak), and open cover (open): area-weighted mean patch size (AREA), clumpiness index (CLUMPY), area-weighted mean Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance (ENN), interspersed and juxtaposition index (IJI), largest patch index (LPI), percentage of land cover (PLAND), and mean proximity index (PROX). We also assessed forest cover strata (STRATA; $\leq 20\%$ forest, >20 to $\leq 40\%$ forest, >40 to $\leq 60\%$ forest, >60 to $\leq 80\%$ forest, and $>80\%$ forest) and the following landscape configuration metrics (McGarigal et al. 2012): edge density (EDGE), contrast-weighted edge density (CWED), IJI, and contagion index (CONTAG).

^b Detection probability covariates ($p\{\text{best}_n\}$) from the best-supported model for wild turkeys in northern Wisconsin (Survey Period, Time², Wind, and [Time $\times$ Wind]; Table 1).

^c Top-supported models ($\Delta\text{AIC}_c < 2$) within the local availability model set which were further used as the base models in the subsequent model set to evaluate route occupancy of wild turkeys in northern Wisconsin (Table 3).

^d Best-supported detection probability (p) model for wild turkeys northern Wisconsin (Table 1).

Table 3. Multiseason correlated-replicate model selection results for probability of route occupancy for eastern wild turkeys within 3.2-km buffered (~5,300 ha) gobbling call-count survey routes in northern Wisconsin, USA, 2014–2017. Models were ranked by the difference (ΔAIC_c) between the model with the lowest Akaike’s Information Criterion for small samples (AIC_c) and AIC_c for the current model, K is the number of model parameters, w_i is model weight, and $-2\log(L)$ is the maximized -2 log-likelihood function. Model fit was assessed in Program PRESENCE v12.23 (Hines 2006). Non-converging models are not included within the model set.

Probability of route occupancy model ^a	K	AIC_c	ΔAIC_c	w_i	$-2\log(L)$
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}^b, \pi\{\cdot\}^c$	28	3,129.22	0.00	0.275	3,060.53
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}^c$	30	3,130.82	1.60	0.124	3,056.06
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,131.86	2.64	0.074	3,063.17
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}} + \text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,132.59	3.38	0.051	3,063.91
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,132.72	3.50	0.048	3,061.02
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,132.90	3.68	0.044	3,061.20
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,133.41	4.20	0.034	3,064.73
$\psi\{\text{CWED}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	27	3,133.52	4.30	0.032	3,067.80
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,133.72	4.50	0.029	3,065.03
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	30	3,134.08	4.86	0.024	3,059.32
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,134.82	5.60	0.017	3,063.11
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}} + \text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,134.85	5.63	0.017	3,063.15
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,135.54	6.32	0.012	3,066.85
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,135.59	6.38	0.011	3,063.89
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,135.69	6.48	0.011	3,067.01
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{CWED}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,135.70	6.49	0.011	3,064.00
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,135.79	6.57	0.010	3,067.10
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,135.82	6.61	0.010	3,064.12
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,135.89	6.67	0.010	3,067.20
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	27	3,136.14	6.92	0.009	3,070.42
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,136.23	7.02	0.008	3,067.55
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,136.25	7.03	0.008	3,067.56
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,136.36	7.14	0.008	3,067.67
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	28	3,136.37	7.15	0.008	3,067.68
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	27	3,136.51	7.29	0.007	3,070.78
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	29	3,136.62	7.40	0.007	3,064.92
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\cdot\}$	27	3,136.83	7.62	0.006	3,071.11

Table 3: route occupancy model set

$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,136.86	7.64	0.006	3,055.82
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,137.17	7.95	0.005	3,062.41
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,137.28	8.06	0.005	3,056.25
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,137.33	8.11	0.005	3,062.57
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,137.41	8.19	0.005	3,062.65
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,137.42	8.20	0.005	3,071.70
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,137.48	8.26	0.004	3,065.78
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,137.63	8.41	0.004	3,062.87
$\psi\{\text{CWED}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,137.81	8.59	0.004	3,066.11
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,138.18	8.96	0.003	3,066.48
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}} + \text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,138.21	8.99	0.003	3,063.45
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,138.51	9.29	0.003	3,072.79
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,138.77	9.56	0.002	3,060.90
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,138.78	9.56	0.002	3,073.06
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,138.87	9.66	0.002	3,070.19
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,138.92	9.70	0.002	3,061.04
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,139.27	10.06	0.002	3,070.59
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,139.62	10.40	0.002	3,070.93
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,139.73	10.51	0.001	3,064.96
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,140.00	10.78	0.001	3,065.24
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,140.21	10.99	0.001	3,074.49
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,140.31	11.10	0.001	3,068.61
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,140.32	11.10	0.001	3,071.63
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,140.35	11.13	0.001	3,062.48
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,140.40	11.18	0.001	3,065.63
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,140.41	11.19	0.001	3,065.65
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,140.48	11.26	0.001	3,074.76
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,140.51	11.29	0.001	3,065.74
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,140.54	11.32	0.001	3,062.67
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,140.62	11.40	0.001	3,065.86
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,140.63	11.41	0.001	3,065.87
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,140.65	11.43	0.001	3,065.89
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,140.71	11.49	0.001	3,065.95
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,140.92	11.71	0.001	3,069.22

Table 3: route occupancy model set

$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,144.11	14.89	0.000	3,069.34
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	29	3,144.17	14.95	0.000	3,072.47
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,144.24	15.03	0.000	3,069.48
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	32	3,144.37	15.15	0.000	3,063.34
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	29	3,144.44	15.22	0.000	3,072.73
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,144.44	15.22	0.000	3,069.68
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	29	3,144.48	15.26	0.000	3,072.78
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,144.54	15.32	0.000	3,069.78
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	27	3,144.75	15.53	0.000	3,079.03
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	28	3,144.80	15.58	0.000	3,076.11
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	29	3,144.81	15.59	0.000	3,073.11
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	29	3,144.95	15.73	0.000	3,073.24
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{AREA}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,145.03	15.82	0.000	3,070.27
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	27	3,145.04	15.82	0.000	3,079.32
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	28	3,145.12	15.90	0.000	3,076.43
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	31	3,145.20	15.98	0.000	3,067.33
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	28	3,145.41	16.19	0.000	3,076.72
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,145.48	16.26	0.000	3,070.71
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	27	3,145.58	16.36	0.000	3,079.86
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	29	3,145.76	16.54	0.000	3,074.06
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,145.88	16.66	0.000	3,071.12
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	31	3,146.41	17.19	0.000	3,068.54
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{AREA}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	31	3,146.42	17.20	0.000	3,068.55
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,146.47	17.25	0.000	3,071.70
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	28	3,146.51	17.29	0.000	3,077.83
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}^d$	28	3,146.62	17.40	0.000	3,077.94
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	27	3,146.74	17.52	0.000	3,081.02
$\psi\{.\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}^d$	26	3,146.77	17.56	0.000	3,083.97
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,146.83	17.62	0.000	3,072.07
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	31	3,146.87	17.65	0.000	3,069.00
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,147.01	17.79	0.000	3,072.25
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	27	3,147.01	17.79	0.000	3,081.29
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,147.08	17.86	0.000	3,072.32
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	31	3,147.08	17.87	0.000	3,069.21

Table 3: route occupancy model set

$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,147.15	17.93	0.000	3,069.28
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,147.20	17.98	0.000	3,078.51
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,147.26	18.04	0.000	3,072.50
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{forest}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,147.29	18.08	0.000	3,075.59
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,147.33	18.11	0.000	3,069.46
$\psi\{\text{EDGE}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,147.36	18.14	0.000	3,081.64
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,147.36	18.14	0.000	3,075.66
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,147.50	18.28	0.000	3,069.63
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,147.51	18.29	0.000	3,066.47
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,147.53	18.31	0.000	3,069.66
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,147.60	18.38	0.000	3,075.89
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,147.66	18.44	0.000	3,069.79
$\psi\{\text{EDGE}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,147.79	18.57	0.000	3,076.09
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,147.88	18.66	0.000	3,082.15
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,148.04	18.83	0.000	3,076.34
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,148.12	18.90	0.000	3,076.42
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,148.15	18.93	0.000	3,082.43
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,148.20	18.98	0.000	3,067.17
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,148.21	18.99	0.000	3,070.34
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,148.27	19.06	0.000	3,082.55
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,148.30	19.08	0.000	3,076.60
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,148.33	19.12	0.000	3,082.61
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,148.37	19.15	0.000	3,076.67
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,148.47	19.25	0.000	3,082.75
$\psi\{\text{CONTAG}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,148.52	19.30	0.000	3,082.80
$\psi\{\text{CONTAG}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,148.55	19.34	0.000	3,076.85
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,148.65	19.43	0.000	3,073.89
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,148.71	19.49	0.000	3,077.00
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,148.71	19.50	0.000	3,077.01
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,148.74	19.52	0.000	3,083.02
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,148.88	19.66	0.000	3,083.16
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,148.89	19.67	0.000	3,083.17
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	28	3,148.98	19.76	0.000	3,080.29
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	27	3,149.11	19.89	0.000	3,083.39

Table 3: route occupancy model set

$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.13	19.92	0.000	3,077.43
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{hard}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.18	19.96	0.000	3,077.48
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{oak}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.23	20.01	0.000	3,077.53
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	27	3,149.24	20.02	0.000	3,083.52
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{AREA}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	32	3,149.29	20.07	0.000	3,068.25
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	30	3,149.29	20.07	0.000	3,074.53
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	27	3,149.29	20.07	0.000	3,083.57
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.31	20.09	0.000	3,077.61
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.34	20.12	0.000	3,077.64
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.44	20.22	0.000	3,077.74
$\psi\{\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{ag}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	27	3,149.48	20.26	0.000	3,083.76
$\psi\{\text{III}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	27	3,149.54	20.33	0.000	3,083.82
$\psi\{\text{LPI}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	28	3,149.57	20.36	0.000	3,080.89
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.59	20.37	0.000	3,077.89
$\psi\{\text{ENN}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.61	20.39	0.000	3,077.91
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	32	3,149.64	20.43	0.000	3,068.61
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	27	3,149.70	20.48	0.000	3,083.97
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	27	3,149.70	20.48	0.000	3,083.97
$\psi\{\text{III}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.78	20.56	0.000	3,078.08
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.79	20.57	0.000	3,078.09
$\psi\{\text{PROX}_{\text{dec}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	29	3,149.79	20.57	0.000	3,078.09
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{grass}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	30	3,150.10	20.88	0.000	3,075.34
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{hard}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	30	3,150.21	20.99	0.000	3,075.45
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	28	3,150.72	21.50	0.000	3,082.03
$\psi\{\text{AREA}_{\text{ag}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	30	3,150.92	21.70	0.000	3,076.16
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	28	3,151.60	22.38	0.000	3,082.91
$\psi\{\text{STRATA}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PROX}_{\text{oak}}\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	30	3,152.17	22.95	0.000	3,077.41
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{dec}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	30	3,152.69	23.47	0.000	3,077.93
$\psi\{\text{STRATA}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{.\}$	32	3,153.95	24.73	0.000	3,072.92

^a Model parameters include route occupancy (ψ), local availability at a survey station given unavailability at the previous station (θ), local availability at a survey station given availability at the previous station (θ'), establishment (γ), abandonment (ε), detection (p), and availability at the unobserved survey station defined by the Markov equilibrium process via θ and θ' (π). Establishment and abandonment parameters were held constant (.) to evaluate the potential influence of land cover covariate(s) on probability of initial route occupancy (ψ) of wild turkeys in northern Wisconsin. Covariates include class-level composition and configuration metrics (McGarigal et al. 2012) for agriculture (ag),

Table 3: route occupancy model set

deciduous forest (dec), forest cover (forest), grass, upland hardwoods (hard), oak, and open cover (open): area-weighted mean patch size (AREA), clumpiness index (CLUMPY), area-weighted mean Euclidean nearest-neighbor distance (ENN), interspersion and juxtaposition index (IJI), largest patch index (LPI), percentage of land cover (PLAND), and mean proximity index (PROX). We also assessed road density (m/ha; ROAD), ratio of open-to-forest cover (O:F), forest cover strata (STRATA; $\leq 20\%$ forest, >20 to $\leq 40\%$ forest, >40 to $\leq 60\%$ forest, >60 to $\leq 80\%$ forest, and $>80\%$ forest), and the following landscape configuration metrics (McGarigal et al. 2012): edge density (EDGE), contrast-weighted edge density (CWED), IJI, and contagion index (CONTAG).

- ^b Detection probability covariates ($p\{\text{best}_n\}$) from the best-supported model for wild turkeys in northern Wisconsin (Survey Period, Time², Wind, and [Time $\times$ Wind]; Table 1).
- ^c Top-supported models ($\Delta\text{AIC}_c < 2$) within the route occupancy model set which were further used as the base models in the subsequent model set to evaluate establishment and abandonment of wild turkeys in northern Wisconsin (Table 4).
- ^d Parsimonious models ($\Delta\text{AIC}_c < 2$) from the local availability model set for northern Wisconsin (Table 2) used as base models to evaluate potential land cover covariates that influence probability of route occupancy for wild turkeys.

Table 4. Multiseason correlated-replicate model selection results for probability of establishment and abandonment for eastern wild turkeys within 3.2-km buffered (~5,300 ha) gobbling call-count survey routes in northern Wisconsin, USA, 2014–2017. Models were ranked by the difference (ΔAIC_c) between the model with the lowest Akaike's Information Criterion for small samples (AIC_c) and AIC_c for the current model, K is the number of model parameters, w_i is model weight, and $-2\log(L)$ is the maximized -2 log-likelihood function. Model fit was assessed in Program PRESENCE v12.23 (Hines 2006). Non-converging models are not included within the model set.

Probability of establishment and abandonment model ^a	K	AIC_c	ΔAIC_c	w_i	$-2\log(L)$
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}^b, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}^c, \pi\}^d$	32	3,119.28	0.00	0.411	3,038.25
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	34	3,122.66	3.38	0.076	3,035.15
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	29	3,123.58	4.30	0.048	3,051.88
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	33	3,123.84	4.56	0.042	3,039.59
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	34	3,124.05	4.78	0.038	3,036.55
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	35	3,124.25	4.97	0.034	3,033.42
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	31	3,124.74	5.47	0.027	3,046.87
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,124.75	5.48	0.027	3,049.99
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	33	3,124.95	5.67	0.024	3,040.71
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,125.44	6.16	0.019	3,050.67
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	35	3,125.55	6.27	0.018	3,034.72
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	36	3,125.76	6.48	0.016	3,031.56
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,125.97	6.69	0.015	3,051.20
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,126.06	6.78	0.014	3,051.30
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,126.15	6.87	0.013	3,051.39
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Other}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,126.16	6.88	0.013	3,051.39
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	33	3,126.34	7.06	0.012	3,042.10
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	30	3,126.62	7.35	0.010	3,051.86
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	31	3,126.69	7.41	0.010	3,048.82
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	33	3,126.79	7.52	0.010	3,042.55
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	33	3,126.81	7.53	0.010	3,042.57
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	31	3,127.07	7.79	0.008	3,049.20
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	38	3,127.22	7.94	0.008	3,026.10
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	31	3,127.43	8.15	0.007	3,049.56
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	32	3,127.58	8.30	0.006	3,046.54
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	36	3,127.60	8.33	0.006	3,033.40
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta'\{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\}$	32	3,127.67	8.39	0.006	3,046.63

Table 4: route establishment and abandonment model set

$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	36	3,127.68	8.41	0.006	3,033.48
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,127.74	8.47	0.006	3,046.71
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,127.79	8.51	0.006	3,049.92
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	38	3,128.18	8.91	0.005	3,027.07
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,128.36	9.08	0.004	3,044.11
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,128.49	9.21	0.004	3,053.73
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,129.08	9.80	0.003	3,051.20
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}^e$	28	3,129.22	9.94	0.003	3,060.53
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,129.32	10.04	0.003	3,054.56
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	36	3,129.34	10.06	0.003	3,035.14
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	37	3,130.11	10.83	0.002	3,032.48
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,130.23	10.95	0.002	3,049.20
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,130.63	11.35	0.001	3,052.75
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,130.64	11.37	0.001	3,058.94
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,130.65	11.37	0.001	3,049.61
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,130.69	11.41	0.001	3,049.66
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}^e$	30	3,130.82	11.54	0.001	3,056.06
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Other}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,131.08	11.80	0.001	3,059.38
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,131.11	11.83	0.001	3,059.41
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,131.32	12.04	0.001	3,056.55
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	35	3,131.33	12.05	0.001	3,040.50
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,131.41	12.13	0.001	3,059.71
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	40	3,131.50	12.22	0.001	3,023.22
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,131.65	12.38	0.001	3,059.95
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	35	3,131.91	12.63	0.001	3,041.09
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Other}\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,131.94	12.66	0.001	3,060.24
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	29	3,132.03	12.75	0.001	3,060.33
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,132.08	12.80	0.001	3,047.83
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	35	3,132.10	12.83	0.001	3,041.28
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\cdot\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Other}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,132.29	13.01	0.001	3,054.41
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,132.57	13.29	0.001	3,057.80
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,132.58	13.30	0.001	3,057.81
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,132.72	13.45	0.000	3,048.48
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Other}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\cdot\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,132.87	13.59	0.000	3,058.10

Table 4: route establishment and abandonment model set

$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,132.95	13.67	0.000	3,058.19
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,133.09	13.81	0.000	3,055.22
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	34	3,133.09	13.82	0.000	3,045.59
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,133.27	13.99	0.000	3,055.40
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,133.35	14.08	0.000	3,058.59
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,133.45	14.17	0.000	3,055.58
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,133.54	14.26	0.000	3,049.30
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Other}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,133.58	14.30	0.000	3,055.71
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}^2\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,133.67	14.39	0.000	3,058.91
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,133.69	14.41	0.000	3,058.93
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,133.88	14.61	0.000	3,059.12
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,134.03	14.76	0.000	3,059.27
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,134.31	15.03	0.000	3,053.28
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,134.34	15.06	0.000	3,053.31
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	30	3,134.50	15.22	0.000	3,059.74
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,134.64	15.36	0.000	3,053.61
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,134.99	15.72	0.000	3,053.96
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,135.51	16.23	0.000	3,051.27
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,135.61	16.33	0.000	3,057.74
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,135.75	16.48	0.000	3,051.51
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	38	3,135.90	16.62	0.000	3,034.78
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,135.96	16.68	0.000	3,054.93
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,136.04	16.77	0.000	3,058.17
$\psi\{\text{CWED} + \text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,136.11	16.84	0.000	3,055.08
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,136.33	17.05	0.000	3,055.30
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,136.35	17.07	0.000	3,052.11
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,137.15	17.87	0.000	3,052.91
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain}^2\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,137.52	18.24	0.000	3,053.28
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,138.33	19.06	0.000	3,057.30
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	34	3,139.30	20.02	0.000	3,051.79
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Corn} + \text{Grain} + \text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	33	3,139.92	20.64	0.000	3,055.67
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Grain}\}, \varepsilon\{.\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,140.51	21.24	0.000	3,062.64
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{.\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	31	3,140.75	21.47	0.000	3,062.88
$\psi\{\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2\}, \theta, \theta' \{\text{best}_n\}, \gamma\{\text{Snow}\}, \varepsilon\{\text{Snow}\}, p\{\text{best}_n\}, \pi\{\}$	32	3,140.83	21.56	0.000	3,059.80

Table 4: route establishment and abandonment model set

$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ \text{Snow} \}, \varepsilon \{ . \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	31	3,140.98	21.70	0.000	3,063.11
$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ \text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 \}, \varepsilon \{ \text{Snow} \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	35	3,141.49	22.21	0.000	3,050.66
$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ \text{Other}^2 \}, \varepsilon \{ . \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	32	3,141.61	22.34	0.000	3,060.58
$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ \text{Grain} \}, \varepsilon \{ \text{Snow} \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	32	3,142.41	23.13	0.000	3,061.37
$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ \text{Grain} \}, \varepsilon \{ \text{Corn} \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	32	3,142.54	23.26	0.000	3,061.51
$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ . \}, \varepsilon \{ \text{Corn} + \text{Snow} \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	32	3,143.15	23.87	0.000	3,062.11
$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ \text{Grain} \}, \varepsilon \{ \text{Grain} \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	32	3,143.32	24.04	0.000	3,062.29
$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ \text{Grain}^2 \}, \varepsilon \{ . \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	32	3,143.34	24.06	0.000	3,062.31
$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ \text{Grain} + \text{Snow} \}, \varepsilon \{ . \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	32	3,143.64	24.36	0.000	3,062.60
$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ . \}, \varepsilon \{ \text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 + \text{Snow} \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	35	3,144.18	24.90	0.000	3,053.36
$\psi \{ \text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2 + \text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2 \}, \theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}, \gamma \{ . \}, \varepsilon \{ \text{Corn}^2 + \text{Grain}^2 \}, p \{ \text{best}_n \}, \pi \{ \}$	34	3,145.72	26.44	0.000	3,058.21

^a Model parameters include route occupancy (ψ), local availability at a survey station given unavailability at the previous station (θ), local availability at a survey station given availability at the previous station (θ'), establishment (γ), abandonment (ε), detection (p), and availability at the unobserved survey station defined by the Markov equilibrium process via θ and θ' (π). For northern Wisconsin, occupancy covariates include percentage of open cover in quadratic form ($\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2$), percentage of oak forest in quadratic form ($\text{PLAND}_{\text{oak}}^2$), contrast-weighted edge density (CWED), and clumpiness index of grass ($\text{CLUMPY}_{\text{grass}}$; McGarigal et al. 2012). Establishment and abandonment covariates include number of days with snow cover >30 cm from 1 Nov–30 Apr within gobbling call-count survey routes (Snow; NOHRSA 2004), and percentage of row crop agriculture (USDA 2017) planted in corn (Corn), small grains (Grain), or other row crops (Other).

^b Local availability covariates ($\theta, \theta' \{ \text{best}_n \}$) from the top-supported occupancy models ($\Delta\text{AIC}_c < 2$) for wild turkeys in northern Wisconsin ($\text{PLAND}_{\text{open}}^2$ and PROX_{oak} ; Table 2).

^c Detection probability covariates ($p \{ \text{best}_n \}$) from the best-supported model for wild turkeys in northern Wisconsin (Survey Period, Time², Wind, and [Time $\times$ Wind]; Table 1).

^d Best-approximating multiseason correlated-replicate occupancy model for wild turkeys northern Wisconsin. This final model was used to predict the probability of patch-specific occupancy of wild turkeys across the northern Wisconsin study region.

^e Parsimonious models ($\Delta\text{AIC}_c < 2$) from the route occupancy model set for northern Wisconsin (Table 3) used as base models for the current model set to evaluate the influence of snow cover and row crop agriculture on establishment and abandonment of wild turkeys in northern Wisconsin.

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